

Table 1. Physical and chemical properties of ricefield soils in Turkey.

State	Soil depth (cm)	Texture ^a	pH	Organic matter (%)	CaCO ₃ (%)	Total N (%)	Available Olsen P (ppm)	Exchangeable cations (meq/100 g)				CEC (meq/100 g)	DTPA extractable			
								Na ⁺	K ⁺	Ca ⁺⁺	Mg ⁺⁺		Zn (ppm)	Fe (ppm)	Mn (ppm)	Cu (ppm)
Corum	0-20	C	7.4	1.41	9.45	1.36	6.94	1.88	0.42	22.00	9.88	34.18	2.03	41.10	12.72	7.05
	20-40	C	7.5	1.54	10.12	1.06	6.24	1.40	0.46	20.16	8.00	30.02	1.09	42.20	12.27	11.43
	40-60	C	7.3	1.61	9.88	0.94	3.18	0.96	0.31	18.40	11.13	30.80	0.48	40.13	12.00	9.00
Ankara	0-20	C	7.6	2.65	22.23	1.49	7.28	0.34	1.39	26.16	9.13	37.02	2.96	45.00	13.88	5.45
	20-40	C	7.7	1.13	22.37	1.47	3.04	0.20	1.46	24.24	10.37	36.27	3.02	41.00	8.74	8.00
	40-60	C	7.7	2.46	22.00	1.45	4.32	0.12	1.63	13.90	10.00	25.65	2.88	32.86	11.62	5.20
Edirne	0-20	Sil	6.6	1.14	1.52	1.71	7.62	1.32	0.63	10.38	7.10	19.43	1.08	56.25	14.64	2.58
	20-40	Sil	7.0	0.40	11.66	1.43	7.62	0.88	0.36	12.24	6.40	19.88	0.39	40.14	11.12	1.74
	40-60	Sil	7.2	0.34	1.08	1.06	5.30	0.97	0.30	8.20	4.16	13.63	0.45	42.00	12.88	1.11

^a C = clayey, Sil = silty.

Table 2. Effect of Zn on grain yield in Turkey.

Treatment	1981 crop season				1982 crop season				Mean yield (t/ha)	Mean increase (%)
	Corum		Ankara		Corum		Edirne			
	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Increase (%)	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Increase (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%)		
No Zn	4.6 cd	—	3.4 b	—	3.5	—	6.7	—	4.5	—
30 kg ZnSO ₄ basal	5.6 ab	20.9	4.4 ab	30.1	3.8	7.3	7.2	7.2	5.2	15.0
60 kg ZnSO ₄ basal	5.7 a	23.5	4.4 ab	31.0	4.3	21.1	7.1	5.8	5.4	17.9
1% ZnSO ₄ foliar	4.8 bcd	4.0	5.1 a	49.0	3.9	11.9	7.5	11.9	5.3	16.8
1% Zn-EDDHA foliar	5.4 abc	16.6	3.7 b	7.6	3.6	1.5	6.5	-2.7	5.8	4.9
1% ZnSO ₄ seed soak	5.0 abcd	8.3	3.6 b	5.1	3.6	2.6	6.9	2.5	4.8	4.5
ZnO seed coat	4.4 d	-5.1	4.3 ab	25.3	4.0	12.9	6.8	1.8	4.8	6.6
SD	47.3		72.8		47.1		62.4			
CV (%)	9.0		17.7		12.4		9.0			
F	**		*		ns		ns			

^a Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 1% level.

content. Milling recovery increased 67-70% in Corum, 61-66% in Ankara, and 58-62% in Edirne, regardless of Zn applications; the variation was not

significant. The 1000-kernel wt also showed no difference.

A common Zn deficiency exists in the rice production area of Corum.

Farmers have recognized the problem, but thought it a disease, not a nutritional problem. Application of Zn will solve it. □

Effect of Calcutta City waste compost on rice yield

N. Chattopadhyay, M. D. Gupta, and S. K. Gupta, University College of Agriculture, Calcutta University, 35 Ballygunge Circular Road, Calcutta 700019, West Bengal, India

Disposal of city garbage is a continuing problem in Calcutta. Dumping lands are gradually being filled up by city garbage and further dumping is almost impossible. Newly developed, expensive land is being used as garbage dumps, wasting

material wealth and posing health hazards.

Wastes could be converted to compost and used for agricultural purposes. Investigations at the Agricultural Experimental Farm during 1984 and 1985 kharif examined

the possibility of using such compost alone or in combination with urea in rice production.

Characteristics of soil and Calcutta city waste compost, mechanically prepared, are presented in Table 1. N at 120 kg/ha was supplied by urea,

Table 1. Chemical characteristics of soil and compost. Calcutta, India.

	pH	Organic C (%)	Available nutrients (ppm)						
			N	P	K	Zn	Mn	Fe	Cu
Soil	6.2	0.92	94.0	20.3	520.8	0.82	0.55	4.22	0.15
Calcutta City waste compost	8.1	7.50	343.3	374.0	2185.0	147.05	35.00	89.25	29.25

compost, and a urea-compost mixture. Rice varieties Ratna, Subarna, and IET1444 were used. A uniform 50 kg K/ha was applied basally during land preparation. N as urea was applied in three equal splits; the entire amount of compost was added basally. A separate field experiment was conducted for each variety with three replications in a randomized block design.

Compost was effective in increasing yield (Table 2). Ratna gave the best response. Yields with urea were highest in all treatments; yields with compost alone and in combination with urea

Table 2. Response of rice to compost and urea. Calcutta, India.

Treatment	Yield ^a (t/ha)		
	Ratna	Subarna	IET1444
Control (no N)	3.1	3.5	3.7
Compost at 120 kg N/ha	5.2	4.7	5.4
Urea at 120 kg N/ha	5.3	5.1	5.6
Compost at 60 kg N/ha + urea at 60 kg N/ha	5.2	4.9	5.4
CD at 5%	0.2	0.2	0.2

^a Means of 2 yr.

were similar. The effect of compost on yield may be due to its appreciable amounts of N, P, K, Zn, Fe, Mn, and Cu, along with organic matter. In

addition, increased available macro- and micronutrients in the soil ultimately help increase yield. □

Influence of herbicides on biomass production and relative growth rate of *Azolla pinnata*

G. Srinivasan, P. Pothiraj, and D. Purushothaman, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, India

Field and pot culture experiments were used to study the effect of some promising preemergence herbicides on biomass production and relative growth rate (RGR) of azolla. Azolla was inoculated at 200 g/m² and fresh biomass was estimated 15 d later in the field. RGR was calculated from fresh weight in pot cultures at 3-d intervals.

Among the herbicides tried, biomass production was highest with EPTC alone (see table). Butachlor recorded

Effect of some herbicides on azolla biomass production. Coimbatore, India.

Herbicide	Biomass (t/ha) in field	RGR (g/g per d) in pot culture
EPTC	6.69	0.1818
EPTC + 2,4-D ethyl ester (EE)	6.51	0.1994
EPTC + 2,4-D butyl ester (BE)	6.47	0.1810
Molinate + 2,4-D (EE)	5.20	—
Molinate	4.86	—
Thiobencarb	4.05	—
Butachlor	2.96	—
No herbicide (control)	—	0.1974

the least biomass production. Thiobencarb, molinate, and combinations with 2,4-D EE were similar. Biomass production was significantly less than for EPTC and its combinations with 2,4-D esters.

Azolla inoculation 3 d after herbicide application recorded the

highest biomass; that on the day of herbicide application drastically reduced biomass production.

Applying EPTC either alone or in combination with 2,4-D esters and inoculating azolla 3-6 d after application produced the highest azolla biomass and higher RGR. □

Preparation method for carbon dioxide-bicarbonate medium used to culture rice plant in water

T. Higuchi, Laboratory of Agriculture, Faculty of Education, Tokyo Gakugei University, Koganei-shi, Tokyo 184; and N. Murayama, Laboratory of Plant Nutrition and Fertilizer, Faculty of Agriculture, Tokyo University of Agriculture and Technology, Tokyo Fuchu, 183 Japan

The pH value of media used in water culture of rice plants declines rapidly

because of nutrient absorption by rice roots. The pH must be adjusted almost every day, a time-consuming process. A more practical, carbon dioxide-bicarbonate medium, containing large quantities of CO₂ has been developed. Similar conditions exist in field soil solutions.

In the new medium ammonium bicarbonate and potassium bicarbonate are used to lower the proportion of sulfate and chloride salts.

Stock solution A: Dissolve 113 g of ammonium bicarbonate (NH₄HCO₃)

and 31.9 g of potassium bicarbonate (KHCO₃) in 1 liter of distilled or CO₂-saturated water. Stir carefully and slowly to dissolve the chemicals and to prevent formation of heavy foam. Preserve this stock solution in polyethylene or glass bottles.

Stock solution B: Dissolve 40.0 g of Na₂HPO₄ in 1 liter of distilled water.

Stock solution C: Dissolve 36.7 g of MgSO₄·7H₂O in 1 liter of distilled water.

Stock solution D: Dissolve 15.1 g of Fe-EDTA and 10.5 g of CaCl₂·2H₂O in 1 liter of distilled water.